

PART 01

Movelaser

How is your technology addressing (and solving) key challenges of the wind industry today?

- **Accurate Measurement**
- **Flexibility / Portability**
- **Cost Efficiency**
- **Reliability**

Accurate Measurement :

REMOTE SENSING DEVICE VERIFICATION REPORT

RSD Type: Molas B300
Serial No.: MDABAP4803022

PREPARED FOR:
NANJING MOVELASER CO., LTD.

Report Number:
UL-CHN-PPT-25-15700227-RSDV-01.01

Zhangbei Test Site
Hebei Province, China

2025-04-07

CLASSIFICATION
CLIENT'S DISCRETION

ISSUE
01

**Molas B300 V4
UL Verification**

**Molas B300 V4 classification
in process...**

TYPE MOLAS B300 LIDAR Remote Sensing Device Type-specific Classification Summary

Nanjing Movelasar Co., Ltd

Report No.: 10179759-R-04-B
Date: 2021-05-11

**Molas B300 V3
DNV Classification**

B300-970

Comparative assessment on ground-based LiDAR with the serial number Molas B300-970 in complex terrain

Nanjing Movelasar Co., Ltd.

Report No.: 10440511-DNA-R-01
Date: 2024-03-14

**Molas B300
Complex Terrain**

DTU Wind Energy LC 1-141 (EN)

Calibration of ground-based lidar instrument: Molas B300 SN 057

Østerild Test Site

Denmark

Ginka Georgieva Yankova (Measurement Engineer)
Paula Gómez (Review)

DTU - Wind Energy
Riso Campus
Roskilde, Denmark
May 2018

**Molas B300 DTU
Verification**

- **Cost Efficiency**

With the rapid growth of the wind power market, the demand for lidars is rising significantly. Thanks to large-scale production capacity and stable supply chain, we are well positioned to meet this demand. At the same time, mass manufacturing helps reduce the traditionally high cost of lidars and further accelerates their widespread adoption.

- **Flexibility / Portability -- Lighter and smaller**

Easy deployment in complex terrain and offshore environments supports project development where met masts are impractical.

Product	B300 V3	B300 V4	NL5	NL6	3D V1	3D V3
Weight	50kg	50kg	23kg	17.5kg	160kg	130kg
Size	603*500*602mm ³	554*430*576mm ³	512*354*308mm ³	431*290*309mm ³	750*650*1130m ³	735*756*1000m ³

• Environmental Reliability

Robust hardware and advanced correction algorithms (e.g. turbulence, flow distortion) ensure dependable performance in diverse conditions.

Case 1: Desert region with dust

Lidar in Ordos, Inner Mongolia Autonomous Region, North-west of China

Lidar in Tacheng, Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region, North-west of China

#	Height (m)	Data	Valid	Possible	Data Recovery
		Columns	Data Points	Data Points	Rate (%)
1	50	4	121,416	122,692	98.960
2	70	4	121,416	122,692	98.960
3	80	4	121,416	122,692	98.960
4	100	4	121,416	122,692	98.960
5	110	4	121,412	122,692	98.957
6	115	4	121,400	122,692	98.947
7	120	4	121,396	122,692	98.944
8	125	4	121,376	122,692	98.927
9	130	4	121,372	122,692	98.924
10	140	4	121,340	122,692	98.898
11	150	4	121,328	122,692	98.888
12	160	4	121,320	122,692	98.882

Lidar in Ordos

#	Height (m)	Data	Valid	Possible	Data Recovery
		Columns	Data Points	Data Points	Rate (%)
1	40	4	83,144	83,724	99.307
2	60	4	83,384	83,724	99.594
3	80	4	83,448	83,724	99.670
4	100	4	83,408	83,724	99.623
5	105	4	83,384	83,724	99.594
6	115	4	83,336	83,724	99.537
7	120	4	83,316	83,724	99.513
8	125	4	83,272	83,724	99.460
9	140	4	83,036	83,724	99.178
10	160	4	82,464	83,724	98.495
11	180	4	81,344	83,724	97.157
12	200	4	79,284	83,724	94.697

Lidar in Tacheng

Over 98%
Data Reliability
11/05/2023 ~
10/12/2023

Over 97%
Data reliability
under 180m
height
06/06/2024 ~
30/10/2024

Environmental Reliability

Case 2: Heavy rain and fog (2024.7.19-2025.1.3)

Lidar in Jiangxi Province, Middle-west of China

Min. Humidity 28.03%
Max. Humidity 96.3%

Data Reliability during heavy fog and rain over 82%

More than 40% of the testing period is conducted under humidity conditions above 90%.

140m visibility

Environmental Reliability

Case 3: High-altitude, low-temperature and low aerosol

Application : Wind Resource Assessment

Location: Ngari Prefecture, Tibet Autonomous Region, Southwest China 2024.7-2024.9

Coordinate: E 83°36'50.2", N 32°41'4.3"

Altitude: 4949.5 m above sea level

- The data availability **exceeded 90%** at measurement heights ranging from 80m to 160m.
- data availability was significantly reduced at 30m and 50m, mainly due to heavy snowfall obstructing laser transmission, which impacted performance at lower heights.

Environmental Reliability

Case 4: Low temperature

Application : Wind Measurement
Temperature : -34.65°C to 19°C
Location : Hulun Buir
2023.12 - 2024.1

- The 10-minute average data availability **exceeded 95%** at all measurement heights, except for the maximum level at 300m.
- Horizontal wind speeds at adjacent height levels showed strong correlation, with correlation coefficients between **0.92 and 0.98**, further confirming the data reliability and instrument stability.

- Which challenges do you see for the future? (and where can an initiative like Task 52 help your businesses in particular?)
- **Standardization:** As lidar becomes mainstream, industry-wide harmonization of new application, unit testing, type classification, and data acceptance is critical.
- **Complex terrain and offshore applications:** More research is needed to handle flow complexity, turbulence in complex terrain, and extreme weather conditions.
- **Integration with digitalization:** Future wind energy will rely on big data, AI, and fleet-wide monitoring—lidar data must be seamlessly integrated.
- **Task 52's role:** By fostering common testing protocols, sharing best practices, and aligning certification/acceptance processes, Task 52 can accelerate lidar adoption and reduce barriers for developers, OEMs, and operators.